

How does the used vehicle influence the performed manoeuvre? - Insights from an Active Mobility Tracking Experiment on a Test Field

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Abstract:

In numerous urban environments Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) such as pedestrians, cyclists and wheelchair users rely daily on a functioning transport infrastructure. We focus on modern vehicle types such as electric cargo bicycles and electric kick scooters, which face trends in usage especially in highly populated urban environments, and try to discover typical movement patterns. This has the intention to define novel models for simulating traffic flow on respective presently-assigned infrastructure for gaining a further understanding of how these means of active mobility influence other road user types and of which problems might arise from novel movement dynamics of these vehicles. The latter is being addressed by designing vehicle dynamics for reproducing movement of for example electric cargo bicycles in a Virtual Reality (VR) environment (Lindner et al. 2022). In a first step, we investigate breaking and turning manoeuvres of different vehicles for comparing the different trajectories from a field experiment on assigned real test field. Therefore, we equipped several test vehicles with GNSS tracking devices and observed part of the test field via video devices. The experiments consisted of several instructions, which were assigned to a numerous group of test subjects acting as different types of VRUs. Example video frames of one of the experiment are pictured in Figure 1.

Figure 1. A selection of the used active mode vehicles on the field experiment in southern Germany on May 9, 2022.

Previous work (Keler et al. 2021) focussed on acquiring massive trajectory data collections from sensor-equipped (mainly via using GNSS) electric cargo bicycles for comparing quantitatively commuter patterns and the used transport infrastructure influencing shapes and speeds of respective trajectories of every used vehicle. Additional research focussed on testing sensors for measuring the traffic stress level for different VRUs under varying experimental conditions (Vogt et al. 2022).

After data pre-processing, our first results indicate varying velocities of not only different used vehicle, but as well show indications dependent on every individual test person participating in this field experiment. First visualizations of extracted raw trajectories are pictured in Figure 2. Besides these velocity differences, we focus subsequently on changing trajectory shapes within different turning manoeuvres.

Based on these first insights, we classify every vehicle characteristic via averaged values and introduce weighting functions for depicting the variants performed by every individual test subject during the field test.

Figure 2. A selection of plotted trajectories of 3 individual test subjects participating in the field experiment in southern Germany on May 9, 2022, with classified speed values.

In addition to this novel approach of producing massive collections of tracking data, we introduce higher-resolution video cameras for gathering additional raw data that might improve the average GNSS positioning qualities by adding a reference in space by segmenting respective frames by visible vehicle and infrastructural element. In the end, we discuss the usefulness of the different sensors for benefiting to the quality of the overall trajectory dataset.

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